

Towards Zero Code-Waste research

19

Responses

659:46

Average time to complete

Active

Status

1. Institution/organization name

19

Responses

Latest Responses

"KEK"

"Canadian Lightsource"

"Insitut Laue-Langevin"

2 respondents (11%) answered **Sincrotrone Trieste** for this question.

2. I represent

- The organization 1
- Team, group or division (within t... 18

3. Organization type

● National or local	14
● International	5

4. Location of the organization (country)

19
Responses

Latest Responses

"Japan"

"Canada"

"France"

3 respondents (16%) answered **Germany** for this question.

5. How many software developers work within your department

19
Responses

Latest Responses

"4"

"13"

"12"

3 respondents (16%) answered 8 for this question.

6. What common software frameworks does your institute/group use?

- EPICS
- Tango Controls
- BlueSky
- MXCube
- Matlab Middlelayer
- Other

7. Please select up to three technologies that are the most popular within your software team

8. What areas (up to three) of your institute's needs does your team support the most?

9. How much software do you use comes from other institutes or collaborations?

10. In how many collaborative software projects do you actively participate?

None	4
1	3
2 to 5	10
more than 5	2

11. How much effort does your team spend on the development (technical work) of software shared with other institutes

Less than 5% of the team's capp...	7
Between 5 and 20%	9
Between 20 and 50%	1
More than 50%	2

12. How often, on average, do you and your teammates travel to other institutes?

Weekly	0
Monthly	5
Yearly	9
Less than yearly	5

13. How often on average do you and your teammates meet online with other institutes?

Weekly	4
Monthly	11
Yearly	2
Less than yearly	2

14. I have strong support from my institute's management for participation in collaborations.

Promoters	4
Passives	9
Detractors	6

15. My team could share more of the software which we develop.

Promoters	4
Passives	7
Detractors	8

16. My team has enough capacity to support other institutes that use our software.

Promoters	1
Passives	3
Detractors	15

17. If we collaborate more on the software with other institutes, we can better fill our mission towards our institute.

Promoters	2
Passives	9
Detractors	8

18. My team has enough support from other collaborating institutes.

Promoters	1
Passives	7
Detractors	11

19. Outsourcing open-source software development to private companies will help to share the code between institutes.

Promoters	1
Passives	4
Detractors	14

20. Outsourcing the development of shared open-source projects to private companies can speed up software development within the community.

Promoters	1
Passives	6
Detractors	12

21. Internal software development is faster than re-using software developed by other institutes or in collaboration.

22. It is difficult to re-use software developed at other institutes because of a lack of documentation.

23. It is difficult to reuse software developed at other institutes if it is based on technologies we do not have experience with.

24. Reusing software developed at other institutes is difficult because of cultural differences (like naming conventions, language barriers, or others).

25. Reusing software developed at other institutes is difficult because of non-matching requirements.

26. Feel free to share your thoughts with us.

8
Responses

Latest Responses

6 respondents (75%) answered **software** for this question.

